

Data Literacy and Visualization: Improving Undergraduate STEM Education Through Service Learning at Two Institutions

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Abstract

In Fall 2020, the University of Nebraska at Omaha (UNO) successfully introduced a general education quantitative literacy course fusing workforce-critical data science skills with service learning. Seeking to build on UNO's existing success, the University of Washington Tacoma (UWT) created their own version of the course for Spring 2024, with researchers collaborating to revise, implement, and assess it in both environments. At UNO, the proposed model contributed to increased data literacy among participants from a broad variety of majors by helping them develop fundamental mathematical, quantitative, and data literacy competencies in ways that are accessible and engaging, while increasing the capacity of local non-profit organizations to use data to answer meaningful questions to further their missions. Similar outcomes for UWT and its community were predicted, where we expected to find an increase in positive perceptions of mathematics and data science, particularly for non-STEM affiliated students who typically have lower interest and self-efficacy in mathematics and are often from groups underrepresented in STEM. Analysis of data collected at both institutions are presented.

Key Words: data literacy, data visualization, service learning

1. Introduction

Across the country, many introductory undergraduate mathematics courses have high failure rates and represent a barrier to success.¹ Some institutions have attempted to address this problem by redesigning introductory mathematics courses. In Fall 2020, the University of Nebraska at Omaha (UNO) introduced STAT 1100: Data Literacy and Visualization, a new general education quantitative literacy course that combines workforce-critical data science skills with service learning. STAT 1100 leverages UNO's commitment to community engagement by integrating service-learning with mathematics instruction. Students in the course work in groups to analyze and visualize data to answer questions posed by non-profit community partners. Research shows that the course has a significant positive impact on students' attitudes towards math and statistics.^{2,3} Additionally, STAT 1100 has been very successful, with half the failure rate of other GenEd math

courses (14% DFW rate compared to 27%). Additionally, STAT 1100 has a 13% higher ABC rate than non-service learning courses.

STAT 1100 leverages service-learning as an alternative to traditional undergraduate mathematics courses, which suffer from high failure rates and act as a barrier to graduation. Service-learning, a method of experiential education, promotes inquiry by combining classroom instruction with community service. It enhances student engagement and supports learning of foundational quantitative literacy competencies, such as underlying data literacy and visualization, by emphasizing critical thinking and problem solving in the context of real-world experiences generated by partnerships with local non-profits. Additional advantages of service learning include benefitting from the experiences of people with diverse perspectives, frequent feedback, opportunities to demonstrate competence, as well as opportunities for reflection.^{4,5}

Students who are historically underserved by higher education yield even greater gains with high-impact educational practices than their advantaged peers.² However, as it pertains specifically to mathematics, lower-division mathematics courses have a disproportionately high failure rate, but they often serve as a prerequisite for STEM degrees.^{3,6} Yet, research shows that better math performance is associated with positive school outcomes in STEM fields.¹ Through this course, students meet general education requirements in quantitative literacy, develop data literacy and visualization skills, and increase their confidence and interest in mathematics, data science, and community engagement. Additionally, faculty develop a new approach to general education mathematics courses that includes service learning. Finally, community partners build their organizational capacity for data literacy and visualization.

Similar challenges and shared characteristics such as a commitment to community engagement brought together UNO and the University of Washington Tacoma (UWT). UWT faculty who seek to build on the existing success of STAT 1100 have created their own version of the course (TCORE 122). UNO and UWT researchers are collaborating to revise, implement, and assess the course in both environments. We are specifically interested in investigating the conditions necessary for successfully replicating the success of service learning for data literacy and visualization. Success is defined in terms of students' performance in the course as well as their interest and engagement in mathematics and other STEM disciplines. We also seek to understand the impact on students' skills and attitudes relating to data and data analysis. Specifically, we seek to answer these questions:

- What challenges arise, and what supports are necessary, to implement new versions of Data Literacy and Visualization at UWT and UNO, particularly in terms of course pacing and finding community partners?
- What course modifications will arise through the collaborative replication process? How will those modifications facilitate implementation in different contexts?
- Are new versions of the course as successful as the original in terms of student competency and attitudes with mathematics, data science, and STEM? What factors might account for any variation?
- To what extent does STAT 1100 / TCORE 122 increase students' data literacy and data science skills?

At UNO, the proposed model has already contributed to increased data literacy among participating students from a broad variety of majors by helping them develop fundamental mathematical, quantitative, and data literacy competencies in ways that are accessible and engaging. It also increases the capacity of local non-profit organizations to use data to answer meaningful questions to further their missions.

TCORE 122 was offered in during the Spring 2024 at UWT, and we predicted similarly positive outcomes for students and the Tacoma community. As at UNO, we found an increase of positive perceptions of mathematics and data science, particularly for non-STEM affiliated students who typically have lower interest and self-efficacy in mathematics and are often from groups underrepresented in STEM. In today's data-driven world, foundational data literacy skills are important for everyone, not just those who pursue careers in data science.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Inquiry-Based Learning

Inquiry-based learning (IBL) describes a spectrum of active-learning practices with certain key features: students engage in rich mathematics and have opportunities to collaborate, while instructors inquire into student thinking and facilitate equitable engagement.^{4,5,6} The Conference Board of the Mathematical Sciences (CBMS) has called for the investment of time and resources into ensuring that active-learning strategies are incorporated into college mathematics classrooms.⁷ IBL is associated with teaching mathematics for deeper understanding^{8,9} and can have a significant and persistent positive impact on undergraduate women in mathematics as well as previously lower-achieving students.¹⁰

Like IBL, service learning encourages students to engage in authentic inquiry by solving real-world problems and documenting learning through regular conversation and reflection. A strength of this project is the integration of IBL and service learning, with students conducting inquiry using data from the community partners. In Data Literacy and Visualization, groups of students demonstrate deep understanding of the data and mathematical manipulations necessary to answer questions in collaboration with community partners, who can use the results to increase their capacity to fulfill their missions.

2.2 Service Learning

Service learning is a method of experiential education that combines classroom instruction with meaningful, community-identified service. This form of engaged teaching and learning emphasizes critical thinking by using reflection to connect course context with real-world experiences. The student learning outcomes in a service learning course are established by the discipline; however, the students attain the outcomes in the context of community partners' authentic needs.

Researchers have demonstrated the positive effects of service learning courses on higher education student outcomes such as academic performance,¹¹ personal development/efficacy,^{12,13} critical thinking,¹⁴ and enhanced civic engagement.^{15,16} Service learning, one of Kuh's identified "high-impact practices," has the ability to impact student success by increasing student retention and engagement.^{17,18} Higher education students engaged in service learning courses become more informed citizens and grow skills essential to serving and sustaining our diverse democracy.^{19,20,21} The development of civic skills in education also connects to Dewey's educational theory,²² in which learning and experience are connected both to social action and community progress.²³ Service learning can build students' civic skills that encourage them to be "actors rather than spectators" in their communities,²⁴ and after service learning experiences, students report they are more likely to be involved in the community.²⁵ The civic outcomes of service learning connect directly with the public purposes of higher education institutions: to prepare leaders for their communities²⁶ and better understand community issues.²⁷

2.3 Need for Data Literacy

Data literacy is the "ability to read, work with, analyze, and argue with data."²⁸ Organizations benefit if employees are data literate, leading to claims that "the ability to 'speak data' will become an integral aspect of most day-to-day jobs."^{29,30} Foundational data literacy skills can be used by students throughout their university coursework and then conveyed into the workforce, where the skills can be used in a variety of settings beyond pure data analytics careers.³¹

Just as literacy, in the context of language, is defined as the ability to read and write using words, data literacy refers to the ability to read and write, i.e., *communicate*, with data. A primary means of doing this is visualizations, which help individuals see patterns and grasp difficult concepts that are not obvious from the raw data. Research has shown that although individuals are interested in visualizations, for example at museums, they have significant limitations in understanding them.³²

As with any form of literacy, analyzing data and producing visualizations (which is analogous to writing) is more difficult than simply reading and understanding.

3. Institutional Contexts and Background

3.1 University of Nebraska-Omaha and STAT 1100

University of Nebraska-Omaha (UNO) is the largest institution of higher education in the Omaha metropolitan area, which has a population of 865,000 and is the most populated area in Nebraska, representing approximately 30% of the state's overall population. UNO is a Carnegie Doctoral University: High Research Activity that has a total undergraduate enrollment of 12,566 and a graduate enrollment of 3,032 (Fall 2022). Roughly 36% of students are from underrepresented groups, and 40% of new students are first generation college students.

In 2011, faculty at UNO redesigned its high-enrollment introductory mathematics course (MATH 1310). Students attended only one lecture per week and spent most of their course time in the math lab, using interactive e-books, homework, and assessment systems to work through problems at their own pace. Teaching assistants provided support. While these revisions increased success rates by 5–12% per semester, the overall percentage of grades of D or F or of students withdrawing from the course entirely (DFW rate) remained higher than 30%, especially after the course was redesigned and renumbered. And while the math lab format helped students *pass* the introductory course, students still saw it as a course to “get through.” Students didn't learn to appreciate the beauty of mathematics and mathematical thinking, and weren't inspired to continue studying math. In short, most students didn't like math before taking the course, and they still didn't like it afterward. Very few students went on to take any further mathematics courses and only 2% proceeded to take Calculus 1, which is required for many STEM majors.

In 2017, an interdisciplinary team of UNO faculty set out to address this problem by designing, implementing, and assessing a new interdisciplinary STEM course that integrated computer science, art, and mathematics (MATH 1120). The development of this course revolutionized the university's GenEd requirements. While the previous *mathematics* requirements focused on algebraic outcomes, the new *quantitative literacy* requirements require UNO graduates to demonstrate competency in using mathematical, computational, or statistical methods. Research measured its effectiveness at changing student attitudes towards STEM. As anticipated, the course was associated with positive outcomes for students, with students having significantly increased confidence in their mathematical ability³³ ($p < 0.01$) and math sense of belonging³⁴ ($p < 0.01$). This outcome was reinforced by post-course “mathography” reflections, which emphasized how the course changed students' understanding of what math is. Students move from rote memorization of formulae to understanding real-world applications of patterns and other mathematical concepts. Pre-course mathography reflections³⁵ showed that many students have a traumatic history with mathematics, often feeling unsuccessful and incapable. Post-course mathographies showed they felt well-supported³⁶ and were willing to seek help during class and office hours—behaviors uncommon in this population. Students were more likely to go on to take STEM courses, especially programming courses, than students in college algebra.

However, while MATH 1120 has proven to engage students' interest early in the course, some students had difficulty maintaining interest and momentum over the semester. Students who attend class and submit assignments consistently have their attitudes about math and STEM changed. But the course has not been as successful in reducing the DFW rate. Furthermore, while students used inquiry-based methods to solve problems, developing valuable mathematical and computing skills, the problems they are asked to solve are not themselves “real-world” problems.

STAT 1100: Data Literacy and Visualization, a new GenEd quantitative literacy course, was designed to address these challenges. STAT 1100 leveraged the university commitment to community engagement by integrating service learning with mathematics instruction. The course is built around projects wherein student groups analyze and visualize data to answer questions

posed by non-profit community partners. The course was designed to meet the following student learning objectives:

1. Students will understand the various types of data and how they can be used to create value for an organization.
2. Students will be familiar with various sources and formats of data.
3. Students will understand the meaning and how to compute summary data statistics.
4. Students will understand the elements of effective data display.
5. Students will develop skills in using tools to create data products.

Project findings demonstrate a significant impact on students' attitudes towards math and success in passing the course.^{37,38} However, the prior project did not evaluate students' *learning* of data literacy, analysis, or visualization.

3.2 University of Washington Tacoma and TCORE 122

University of Washington Tacoma (UWT) is a public urban-serving university and is considered an anchor institution in the South Puget Sound region. Primarily an undergraduate campus (85%), UWT serves approximately 4,800 students with over 50 undergraduate and 15 graduate programs. UWT's history as an upper-division, transfer-only institution is manifested in the more than 50% of its students who transfer from local community colleges or other universities. 51% of undergraduate students are first-to-college or first-to-degree, 49% are low income as defined by Pell grant eligibility, 33% are underrepresented minorities in STEM, 50% of students are female, and 18% are military-affiliated. UWT qualifies as a minority-serving institution (AANAPISI), as classified by the U.S. Department of Education. 61% are students of color, of which 32% are underserved students of color.

UWT learned about STAT 1100 through informal conversation between UNO's Dr. Love and her former student, UWT's Dr. Kmail. Subsequently, the UWT Division of Science and Mathematics expressed interest in implementing the course in UWT's Core Program, which represents various academic programs across the campus and whose aim is to prepare students for upper division classes by focusing on learning goals such as self-expression and communication; community engagement; critical analysis; expanding and diversifying global perspectives and cultural views; and the ability to problem solve. TCORE 122: Data Literacy and Visualization was approved in Winter 2024 with an introductory science designation and a pilot section of the course was offered in Spring 2024, which provided support for expansion of the course to more students, meaningful collaboration between the instructors at each institution, and educational research to understand the impacts of a different context.

TCORE 122 uses service-learning as the context for developing students' data science and quantitative reasoning skills through authentic inquiry-based learning using the same student learning objectives as STAT 1100 at UNO. TCORE 122 implements a mix of teaching methods, focusing on active learning strategies. Some class sessions included brief lecture components, but students spent most of their class time working on problems in small groups, with the instructor role as providing support and answering questions. The early part of the semester focused on core statistical concepts such as measures of central tendency, plotting data, and how to investigate trends in data sets, using Excel. Students were then introduced to Tableau, business intelligence software that allows users to explore, analyze, and visualize data through an easy-to-use drag-and-drop interface. Beyond the impact on students' 21st century workforce skills in data science, the course supported the local Tacoma community by providing answers to partners' questions, increasing the capacity of local non-profit organizations.

Similar to UNO's STAT 1100, student attitudinal changes were measured via a pre-course survey and a corresponding post-course survey in TCORE 122, using validated measures of self-efficacy, interest, and STEM attitudes. Outcomes were compared across institutions in order to investigate differences between implementations. Data collection and analysis employed a mixed-methods approach that uses quantitative data to measure progress towards participation targets, and qualitative data to gain nuanced understanding of individuals' experiences.

4. Results

The pilot section of TCORE 122 enrolled 11 students who worked with two community partners: Safe Streets and Associated Ministries. Safe Streets is a local non-profit committed to community organization and development which connects youth, neighborhood groups, and businesses through services like after-school programs. Their mission is to build strong, safe, and healthy communities. Associated Ministries is a non-profit that works with interfaith partners to develop lasting solutions to homelessness. Support for making connections for the service-learning projects was facilitated through UWT's Office of the Chancellor as well as the Office of Community Partnerships.

Safe Streets was interested in identifying where graffiti occurs in Tacoma and the response times of the city in cleaning the graffiti (Figure 1). They discovered that it takes significantly longer for graffiti to be removed in some zip codes. In fact, while the median response time was two to three days in some zip codes, it was nine days in others. That is, in half of cases of graffiti in low socio-economic areas of the city, the response time is longer than the legal limit (which is nine days).

Figure 1: Tableau visualization of graffiti counts by zip code between 2019 – 2022 created for presentation to Safe Streets

Associated Ministries asked students to investigate the demographics of homelessness in Tacoma. The students investigated demographics including race, veteran status, experiences of domestic violence, and the location of where people had last lived (Figure 2). Associated Ministries is interested in trying to understand what factors might be impacting homelessness in order to identify potential interventions. This is a very large data set, and Associated Ministries plans to continue partnering with TCORE 122 in order to ask deeper and more targeted questions raised by the initial analysis.

Figure 2: Tableau visualization of counts of last permanent address by zip code created for presentation to Associated Ministries

With such a small set of participants, there were no statistically significant survey results. Students in TCORE 122 were somewhat more likely to agree that they would choose a career that used math after taking the class (pre-course: 3.8 out of 5, post-course: 4.3 out of 5).

5. Challenges and Future Work

Some of the challenges that were surfaced during the pilot of TCORE 122 included issues around timing and institutional structures. First, while UWT is on a quarter system, UNO is on a semester system. The teaching teams at both institutions will work together to ensure consistency across the courses, while adjusting the curriculum for the shorter 10-week quarter. While the amount of class time is approximately the same in both systems (37.5 classroom hours for semester, versus 40 hours per quarter), pacing will differ. Second, UNO's implementation of STAT 1100 has relied on the Service Learning Academy (SLA) to find suitable community partners. Although UWT has a strong commitment to community engagement and service-learning, it has no analogous structure. Determining how much effort and support is required to establish community partnerships is necessary for informing the broader impact of the course. Understanding how much effort it takes for a university without the SLA to develop partnerships, and identifying the mechanisms by which those partnerships are established, will help other universities determine what resources are necessary to successfully implement the course.

The future of the Data Literacy and Visualization course at UWT looks bright. In July, UNO and UWT submitted a Tier 2 proposal to the National Science Foundation (NSF) for an IUSE grant with Dr. Kmail and Dr. Maureen Kennedy affiliated with the project at UWT in the role of Co-PI and senior personnel, respectively, to continue the project. In August, Dr. Kmail presented the results from the UWT course pilot at the Joint Statistical Meetings (JSM) in Portland, OR with a publication in the conference proceedings forthcoming. Additionally, faculty at UWT are currently developing a Statistics and Data Science major to fulfill a Bachelor of Science in SIAS in the Division of Math and Sciences. Work on the full program proposal by the Statistics Major Committee is on track to be submitted during the upcoming academic planning cycle. TCORE 122 has been designed as a GenEd course that exposes undergraduate students to topics in data visualization. Because it requires no prerequisite knowledge of statistics or mathematics, it casts a wide net for interested students. While the primary goal of STAT 1100/TCORE 122 is to increase data literacy for non-STEM

students, in some cases STAT 1100 has acted as a gateway to further study of statistics. The hope is that it would provide a similar introduction for students at UWT, as well.

Plans to facilitate the dissemination of results around the Data Literacy and Visualization course are integral to its future. The project team will capitalize on connections and other professional networks to ensure that curricular materials, professional development resources, research findings, and project outcomes are effectively disseminated locally, regionally, and nationally. To share findings and encourage others to change their practice, the project team will present within the mathematics departments and through the STEM Ecosystems about using service-learning as a context for GenEd math. Beyond Omaha and Tacoma, workshops will be delivered at professional meetings, which provide a great venue for sharing our model with mathematicians and mathematics educators from all over the world. The team will also disseminate research findings through peer-reviewed educational journals.

6. Conclusion

At both institutions, the model developed for the Data Literacy and Visualization course has already contributed to increased data literacy among participating students and their community partners. It develops fundamental mathematical, quantitative, and data literacy competencies in ways that are accessible and engaging to students from a broad variety of majors. It also increases the capacity of local non-profit organizations to use data to answer meaningful questions to further their missions. The positive outcomes demonstrated at UNO have already begun to translate to UWT students and the Tacoma community. A positive experience in this gateway course led to more positive perceptions of mathematics and data science as well as an increased commitment to community engagement independent of the setting. Furthermore, the course contributes to increased data literacy among participating students and their community partners—and in today’s data-driven world, such foundational data literacy skills are important for everyone, not just those who pursue careers in data science. By targeting students who are non-STEM majors, the course engages students who typically have lower interest and self-efficacy in mathematics, many of whom are from groups that are underrepresented in STEM.

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